

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15651339

Impact Of Class Size On Effective Teaching And Learning Of English Language In Upper Basic Schools In Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State Nigeria

¹Dauda Ladi & ²Prof. Isaac A. Msheliza

¹Department of Education Foundation,
Taraba state University Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria
ladisam1982@gmail.com 08062933367

²Department of Education Foundations,
Faculty of Education, Federal University Kashere, Gombe State
isaacmsheliza@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of class-size on effective teaching and learning of English language in upper-basic schools in Jalingo education zone. Taraba state Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The study was carried out in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State. The population of the study consists 151 English teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. The sample consists of 108 teachers determined by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample determination. Sampling was carried out using simple random sampling. The instrument for data collection titled “Teaching and Learning of English language Questionnaire (TLELQ) consists of 20 items on a four-point scale of Strongly agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D) and Strongly disagree (1). To test for reliability, Cronbach Alpha was used to test internal consistency, which yielded a coefficient of 0.87. Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using Chi square. The study found that there is significant impact of class size on teacher- students’ interaction during English language lesson. It was concluded that class size influences effective teaching and learning of English language. The study recommended that Workshops and seminars should be regularly organized for teachers to enable them share their experiences and strategies in teaching large classes, and to adopt effective teaching and classroom management techniques, especially for large classes.

Keywords: Class size, effective teaching, Teacher-student Interaction class room observation,

INTRODUCTION

Education is regarded as the bedrock of every nation development. In the whole world and particularly in Nigeria, education has been considered the corner stone for development. It forms the basis for literacy, skill acquisition, technological advancement and ability to harness human and material resources towards the achievement of societal goal (FRN, 2014). The goal of education is to equip students with new skills, knowledge, cultures, attitudes, behaviors and innovative ways of solving day to day problems in life.

According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization cited in Wangui, Ombui and Iravo (2016) education is aimed at supplying the economy with human capital that can convert efficiently for other resources into output of high value for quality life. The philosophy for Nigeria education is based on the integration of the individual into a sound and effective citizen and providing equal educational opportunities for all citizens of the nation at primary, secondary and tertiary levels (FRN, 2014). Therefore, to attain quality education for sustainable development, students must be well taught English language as the core language which is needed for acquisition of knowledge at all the school levels.

English language is regarded as a core and compulsory subject because it is the Lingua Franca or in Nigeria (Anakwue, 2021). English language which is the official language in Nigeria and the general language of communication among Nigerians is a medium of instruction in schools. This makes it a compulsory subject and a prerequisite to gaining admission into tertiary institutions. This points to the important place occupied by the English language in the life of a student in the country. It is, therefore, important for the teacher to develop students' positive attitudes regarding the English language as a school subject and a tool of the language of wider communication (LWC) to enhance their academic performance in the language. Some scholars have given credence to the notion that English language is very crucial to the Nigeria education system since it is not only the medium of instruction especially at the upper primary, secondary and tertiary level of education but also the language of text-books (Aina & Olanipekun, 2014). Yet, being assimilated into the English culture is not synonymous with the mastering of the language. English Language as a subject encompasses the study of English in its various forms and uses. It involves the exploration of grammar, vocabulary, reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills. Study of English as a subject is crucial for effective communication, critical thinking, and cultural awareness. However, the relationship between class size and the quality of English education highlights the need for optimal learning environments to maximize student engagement and success.

Class size is an educational tool that can be described as an average number of students per class in a school (Adeyemi, 2018). Class size according to Ehrenberg, Brewer, Gamorran and Williams (2015) refers to the actual number of pupils taught by a teacher at a particular time and these definitions implies that class size is the number of students per teacher in a class – that's student to tutor. This ratio is a tool that can be used to measure performance of the education system and work productivity. Adeyemi cited in Adolphus, and Godgift (2022) defined class size as an educational tool that can be described as an average number of students in a given course or class room, specifically either the number of students being taught by individual teachers in a course or classroom or the average number of students being taught in a school or educational system. Class size are often mentioned by experts in the educational literature as having effects on students' feelings and performance, quality of school budgets and administration as well (Adimonyemma, Akachukwu & Igboabuchi, 2018). It is considered as one of the important determinants of academic performance over which teachers in schools have little or no control.

Studies have found that the size of a class where students were found smaller in size performed better than those in large classes (Swift, 2015). Small class size often encourages better interaction between the teacher and the students which benefits students in terms of high performance (Schneidier, cited in Kusi & Manful, 2019). Advocates of small classes believes that small class size allow teacher to give more individualized attention to students, manage their classrooms more effectively and provide more effective instruction that leads to better students' performance. The National Policy on Education (2014) states that the teacher-pupil ratio shall be 1:25 for pre-primary education; 1:35 for primary education and 1:40 for secondary education but it is observed that the number of students per class in most schools, especially public schools nowadays is at variance with the dictates of the National Policy on Education.

It is common to see overcrowded classrooms in schools with hard space for teachers to move round let alone the students. In most of our secondary schools in Taraba state and Nigeria today as observe by the researcher, the teacher-student ratio has gone far beyond the stipulation of the National Policy on Education. Students ratio to teachers is more than fifty (1:50) in each class. Educational planners in Nigeria have attributed the over bloated class size due to the explosion of population of children of school age (Garba, Shika & Tukur, 2023). The class size is standard in a situation where the number of students

in a class is neither too much nor too small. Overpopulation of most of our schools may lead to a negative impact on effective teaching and learning.

Effective teaching can be said to be a situation whereby every required material or resources essential for meaningful learning to take place are readily available at the disposal of both the teachers' and students. Effective teaching and learning requires a proper proportion of students to teacher, conducive classroom environment, adequate learning resources, quality of the teacher, ability of the students, class size among others are some of the many variables affects effective teaching and learning in any ideal classroom (Ihekoronye, 2020). However, in most schools, ineffective teaching is due to conditions such as lack of resources facilitating teaching and alarming and overcrowded classrooms (class size). However, understanding individual difference for effective teaching may require taking into consideration on teacher-students' interaction, classroom management, academic performance and use of instructional strategies.

Teacher-student Interaction has an impression on classroom management and affects learning and growth. According to developmental perspective, the establishment of a positive teacher-student relationship aids a student's cognitive, social and emotional growth and enhances their mental well-being. The teacher-student relationships impact productively on a student's self-esteem and enhance their skills. Student-Teacher interactions are vital for the event of the students' academic self-concept and enhancing their enthusiasm and success. Informal interaction between students and school has been identified as a primary agent of school culture, and has a crucial influence on the attitudes, interests, and values of school students (Sen, 2021). The significance of teacher-student interpersonal relationships has been widely recognized in research addressing kindergarten, primary and secondary education. Positive teacher-student interaction is often defined by shared acceptance, understanding, affection, intimacy, trust, respect, care and cooperation..

Instructional strategies are important in implementing the curriculum because they are the means of reaching the predetermine ends (Erionosho, 2013). Instructional strategies methods refer to the general principle, pedagogy and management techniques used for classroom instruction (Kolesnikova, 2016). There are several teaching methods in the field of education. O'banon (2016) categorized teaching method into two approaches; namely the learner centered and the teacher centered approach. The students centered approaches are based on constructivism and includes all the instructional methods that underscores teachers as decision makers and problem solvers but rather as a guide in the teaching process. Student centered methods include discussion, guided inquiry, problem based learning and project. The teacher centered methods of teaching do not promote skill acquisition, objectivity and critical thinking ability among students. Excessive dependence on teaching methods that are teacher centered make cramming the main method of learning which is characterized by repetition and replication of facts culminating into rote learning. The outcome of teacher centered methods of teaching is poor performance especially in science subjects (Berkely, 2015). In Jalingo Education Zone, it is observed that students are faced with trying situations like sitting on the floor to learn and take notes, poor ventilation, poor concentration and overcrowding. This has generated a public concern because this could in turn leads to poor performance of students in English language at secondary schools in Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) and Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and consequently their failure to meet the entry requirement for the Nigerian universities. Bases on the outline background the study seek to examine the impact of class size on effective teaching and learning.

Bagu (2023) investigated the effect of class size on the effective teaching and learning of computer in Junior Secondary Schools in Ushongo, Benue State, using a mixed-methods approach, including both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. A sample of 300 students was selected using simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaires, interviews, and observation checklists. The study found that large class size negatively affects the quality of teaching and learning of computer. Similarly, Adolphus and Godgift (2022) investigated class size influence on teaching and learning of basic science in Junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The purposive sample technique was used to select 223 Basic Science students and 17 teachers of Basic Science. Four research questions were answered. The research

instrument used for data collection was a self-structured close ended questionnaire titled “Class Size Influence on teaching and learning of Basic Science Questionnaire” with four sections addressing each research question. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The study found that small class sizes have a positive influence on teaching and learning of Basic Science while large classes negatively influence teaching and learning of the subject in schools.

Ishii (2021) conducted a study on the effect of class size on teacher-student interaction was investigated in two studies on Hiroshima University students Japan. It was found that teacher revealed more receptional and directed teaching behavior in big class than small and middle class. In study second, it was found that teacher's heart rate were lower in middle class (20 children) than both big and small class. This result indicated that relative to big and small class, teacher in middle class felt easiness with teaching. With respect to hypothesis, there was no clear result of age differences.

Blatchford, Bassett and Brown (2021) conducted a research by comparing effects on pupil classroom engagement and teacher pupil interaction, and examining if effects vary by pupil attainment level and between primary and secondary schools in London. Systematic observations were carried out on 686 pupils in 49 schools. Multilevel regression methods were used to examine relationships between class size and observation measures, controlling for potentially confounding factors like pupil attainment. Classroom engagement decreased in larger classes, but, contrary to expectation, this was particularly marked for lower attaining pupils at secondary level.

Barde, Abubakar, Mohammed, Bizi, Ibrahim, and Uzoma, (2021) carried out a study on the evaluation of the effects of over-population on teaching and learning of among students in junior secondary schools in Potiskum Local Government Area. 3 research questions in line with purpose of the study were formulated. Descriptive Survey Research Design was adopted for the study. Stratified Random Sampling Technique was adopted to select 40 teachers from the 4 junior secondary schools in Potiskum Local Government Area. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation for the questionnaires. The findings of the study revealed that, inability of teachers to pay attention to individual students that need special attention, lack of classroom control and management at overcrowded classroom and teachers found it difficult in conducting effective continuous assessment in classroom are some of the problems faced by teachers and students in teaching and learning in over-populated classrooms in junior secondary schools of Potiskum Local Government Area. The findings of the study also revealed that, high numbers of the students in classroom affect academic performance and that smaller class's size lead to improvement of academic performance are some of the effects of over-population on the quality of teaching and learning in junior secondary schools in the study area.

Aoumeur (2017) studied the impact of class size on teaching and learning English as a foreign language. The investigation was conducted at the department of English at Abdelhamid Ibn Badis University. It used a descriptive survey design. Questionnaires were administered to 200 students and 40 teachers. The finding of the survey shows that large class sizes have an adverse impact on the quality of teaching and learning. Ajayi, Audu and Ajayi (2017) studied the influence of class size on students' classroom discipline, engagement and communication. A sample of 128 senior secondary school teachers from 16 purposely selected secondary schools out of a population of 4529 senior secondary teachers from Ekiti State, Nigeria was used for the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The instrument used for data collection was influence of Class Size on Classroom Discipline, Engagement and Communication Questionnaire (ICSCDECQ) with the reliability value of 0.78 using Cronbach Alpha. Four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Mean rating and Standard Deviation scores as well as Chi-square were used for analysis. The study revealed that class size has significant influence on senior secondary classroom discipline, engagement and communication.

Taofeek , Onifade, and Bello (2016) carried out a study to investigate the impact of class size on students' attitude to studies and teacher- student interaction using four (4) selected secondary schools in Abeokuta, Ogun State Nigeria. Questionnaires were administered to three hundred and sixty (360) students selected evenly from JSS1-SS2 classes in each of the schools. The study found that class size has a highly significant impact on students' attitudes to studies in secondary school ($p < 0.05$). It affects

students' attention most strongly, then punctuality, motivation and participation but not the rate of participation and asking or answering questions and also affect teacher- student interaction.

Kweku and Antwi (2015) in a study investigated the instructional, psychological and social effects large classes have on students of the Department of Basic Education, Winneba, Ghana. The purposive sampling technique was used to select all 893 students in the Department for the 2014/2015 academic year but 642 usable questionnaires were used for the analysis. The findings revealed that the instructional, psychological and social effects of large classes on the students were low even though the social effect was found to have higher mean score than instructional and psychological effects.

Statement of the Problem

It is observed that most of the public secondary schools in Jalingo education zone had experience massive increase of school population in recent time. Therefore, despite the increased students' enrollment rate, public secondary schools' facilities remained unchanged, leading to overcrowding and congested classrooms. The situation may threaten the process of teaching and learning. The observed school population is against the recommended teacher-student ratio in secondary schools of 1:40 which is to enable the teacher as well as the students to interact efficiently. In Jalingo education zone, it is observed that students are faced with trying situations like sitting on the floor to learn and take notes, poor ventilation, poor concentration and overcrowding. This has generated a public concern because this could in turn leads to poor performance of students in English language at secondary schools in Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) and Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and consequently their failure to meet the entry requirement for the Nigerian universities. Thus, many factors have been blamed as the major cause for ineffective teaching and learning of English language as teachers' pedagogical approach, teachers' attitude and students' attitude and generally the laxity in their personal readings have been mentioned as some of the factors responsible. But few studies attempted to look at the class size and how it may impact effective teaching and learning of English language. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the impact of class size on effective teaching and learning of English language in Jalingo Education Zone, with the aim of identifying the key factors that affect language acquisition and proposing possible solutions.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the impact of large class size on effective teaching and learning of English Language in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Determine the impact of class size on teacher-students' interaction in English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state.
2. Examine the impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of class size on teacher- students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state?
2. What is the impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant impact of class size on teacher- students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

HO₂: There is no significant impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

METHODS

The study adopts descriptive survey design. The purpose of descriptive survey research is to examine a phenomenon that is occurring at a specific place and time (Ajai & Amuche, 2015). The study was carried

out in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State, which comprises of two Local Government Areas namely; Jalingo and Ardo-Kola. These local governments were created in 1991 and 1996 respectively. Despite the closeness of the zone to the seat of government where supervision is expected to be on a high level, yet classes are overpopulated. The population of the study consist of 151 English teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Jalingo education zone, Taraba State (Post Primary Schools Management Board, 2024). The sample consists of 108 teachers obtained using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample determination. Simple Random Sampling was used to sample the schools for the study. The instrument for data collection was titled “Teaching and Learning of English language Questionnaire (TLELQ). It consists of 20 items on a four-point scale of Strongly agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D) and Strongly disagree (1) Adapted from Adolphus and Godgift (2022), Garba, Shika and Tukur (2023). The instrument consists of two sections A and B.

The Questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by three experts from Faculty of Education, Taraba State University, Jalingo. Two experts from curriculum instructions and one expert from Measurement and Evaluation. The Questionnaire was subjected to Cronbach Alpha internal consistency test through SPSS version 20.0 which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.87. According to Nurnnally and Bernstein in Igbino (2016), a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.7 and above is considered acceptable. Data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics of mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using Chi square at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of class size on teacher- students’ interaction during English language lesson in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state?*

Table 1: Mean Responses on Impact of Class Size on Teacher Students’ Interaction during English Language Lesson

S/N	ITEMS DESCRIPTION	Mean	SD	Remark
CLUSTER A: CLASS SIZE AND TEACHER-STUDENT INTERACTION				
1	There is always a negative relationship between the teacher and the students in large class size.	3.32	.77	Agree
2	In a small class size there is a positive peer group influence in the teaching/learning of English language.	3.19	.81	Agree
3	There is meaningful student-teacher communication in large class size.	3.48	.66	Agree
4	Large class size encourages students’ social misbehavior.	3.23	.77	Agree
5	Students most of the time feels uncomfortable in large class size.	3.35	.86	Agree
6	Teachers always find it difficult to remember students name in large class size	3.25	1.01	Agree
7	Teachers in small class size are more accessible to the students.	3.29	1.02	Agree
8	Teachers are unable to observe students who are not serious with note taken in large class room.	3.53	.80	Agree
9	Small class size enables to easily identify students who need extra attention during lesson period.	3.52	.80	Agree
10	Large class size increases immoral behaviour among students due to lack of professional supports from teachers.	3.66	.60	Agree
Grand Mean		3.38	0.81	

Source: Field Survey 2025 **n=108**

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics on the opinion of the impact of class size on teacher- students’ interaction during English language lesson in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state. Item by item analysis shows that all the items have mean above 2.5 which is the fixed mean. Also, the grand mean of 3.38 with the corresponding standard deviation of 0.81. This shows that class size impact teachers’ students’ interaction during English lesson

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state?*

Table 2: Mean Responses on Impact of Class Size on Instructional Strategies during English Language Lesson

S/N	CLUSTER C: CLASS SIZE AND INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES	Mean	SD	Remark
11	Teaching of oral English skills in large class size affect teachers' effective instructional activity.	3.07	0.93	Agree
12	Teachers give more attention to students in smaller class size than large class size.	3.17	0.87	Agree
13	The use of audiovisual aids in teaching English language skills makes lesson more captivating on students in large class.	3.00	0.95	Agree
14	The atmosphere of teaching English language in large class size is teacher- centered.	2.96	0.92	Agree
15	Discussion method is often preferable in large class in teaching English language	3.04	0.95	Agree
16	The objectives for teaching/ learning English language skills cannot be achieved in large class size.	3.11	1.01	Agree
17	It is difficult to use collaborative method in teaching English language in large class	3.38	0.78	Agree
18	Inability of teachers to guide students during lesson in large class affect teachers' ability to teach well.	2.94	1.04	Agree
19	Talk and chalk is the only method best in teaching English language in a large class.	3.07	0.93	Agree
20	Small class size improves teachers' effective communication during English language lesson	3.17	0.87	Agree
Grand Mean		3.10	0.93	

Source: Field Survey 2025

n=108

Results of table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation scores of the ratings on impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state. The table shows that all the items have mean above 2.5 including the grand mean of 3.10 with the corresponding standard deviation of 0.93.

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: There is no significant impact of class size on teacher- students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

Table 5: Chi Square Test statistic on Impact of Class Size on Teacher- Students' Interaction during English Language Lesson

Class size	On teacher-students interaction
Chi-Square	731.459 ^a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

The result of the analysis on table 5 shows that there is significant impact of class size on teacher-students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state. Chi square at 3 degree of freedom (731.459; p=.000). Since the computed p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.005 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant impact of class size on teacher- students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

Table 7: Chi Square Test statistic on Impact of Class Size on Instructional Strategies of English Language Teachers

Class size on Instructional	Strategies
Chi-Square	338.911 ^a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

The result of the analysis on table 7 shows that there is significant impact of class size on instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state. Chi square at 3 degree of freedom (338.911, p=.000). Since the computed p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant impact of class size instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion emanating from the results of this study are anchored on the findings of reviewed researches considered in the empirical review section of this work. These discussions are based on the findings on the variables of this study.

The study investigates the impact of class size on effective teaching and learning of English language on upper basic schools students in Jalingo education zone. The study found that all the items have mean above 2.5 which is the fixed mean. Also, the grand mean of 3.38 with the corresponding standard deviation of 0.81. There is significant impact of class size on teacher- students' interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state. This findings agrees with findings of Lin, Zheng and Zhang (2017), Taofeek , Onifade, and Bello (2016) and Ishii (2021) whose found that the interaction between learners and teachers has a significant positive impact on online learners' learning satisfaction as well as on learning effects. The level of teacher–student interaction has a positive impact on learning engagement and psychological atmosphere. Teacher revealed more receptional and directed teaching behavior in big class than small and middle class. Blachford, Basset and Braines (2011) found that there was no statistically significant difference between class sizes for most teachers activities, and teachers did not alter the proportion of time spent interacting with whole class, with groups or with individual.

The findings further indicate that all the items have mean above 2.5 including the grand mean of 3.10 with the corresponding standard deviation of 0.93. There is significant impact of class size instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state. This finding agrees with Adolphus and Godgift (2022), Garba, Shika and Tukur (2023), Bagu (2023) and Adimonyemma, Akachukwu and Igboabuchi (2018) whose findings shows that that teachers find it difficult in a large class to effectively and efficiently assess students during group presentation, individual project or research work, and orally during lesson periods leading to students not being able to learn effectively since low participation during lesson and task were possible. This finding contradict the findings of Kweku and Antwi (2015) who found out that revealed that the instructional effects of large classes on the students were low and there was no significant difference in the views of male and female students on the instructional effect of large classes.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The study examines the impact of class size on effective teaching and learning of English language in upper basic schools in Jalingo education zone. Taraba state Nigeria. To achieve the objectives of the study, two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were used to guide the study. Literature related to impact of class size on effective teaching and learning were reviewed. The review of literatures was based on the variables of the study to give more light and clarification on various terminologies and

concepts in the study and empirical review which established gaps of literatures in the study area, differences in scope as well as some data analysis methods. From a population of 151 English teachers, a sample of 108 teachers was obtained using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample determination. The “Teaching and Learning of English language Questionnaire (TLELQ) was used for data collection. The data collected in the study was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. The study found that there is significant impact of class size on teacher- students’ interaction during English language lesson in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state. There is significant impact of class size instructional strategies of English language teachers in upper basic secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone Taraba state.

Conclusion

The study examined the impact of class size on effective teaching and learning of English language in upper basic schools in Jalingo education zone Taraba state Nigeria. Specifically, the study has shown that class size significantly influences students-teacher interactions, as well as instructional strategies, which in turn influences effective teaching and learning of English language.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are made:

1. Workshops and seminars should be regularly organized for teachers to enable them share their experiences and strategies in teaching large classes, and to adopt effective teaching and classroom management techniques, especially for large classes.
2. School supervisors and inspector should concentrate more on the number of students in each class and avoid overcrowding in classes.
3. The government and the policymakers should plan for resources to be used by the students before their enrolments. This can help to minimize the challenges of inadequate resources for learning and thus promote performance.
4. Government should take in to consideration of the special needs of the school increasing population by funding or increasing the allocation giving to the schools construction of more classes to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, T.O (2018). The influence of class-size on the quality of output in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *American- Eurasian Journal of Scientific Research*, 3 (1), 7-14.
- Adimonyemma N. R., Akachukwu E. E., & Igboabuchi N. A. (2018). Impact of Class Size on Students’ Academic Performance in Biology in Idemili North Local Government Area of Anambra State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 4(8), 124-137.
- Adolphus, T. & Godgift, Precious (2022). Class Size Influence on Teaching and Learning of Basic Science in Junior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 25 (1)13-21.
- Aina, J.K. and Olanipekun, S.S. (2014). The Influence of English Language on Students’ Academic Performance in Physics in Colleges of Education. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 1(2) 271-281.
- Ajai, J.T. & Amuche, C.I. (2015). Educational research methods and statistics. Academic house publishers Nigeria ltd. Ivorcorp Nigeria ltd.
- Ajayi, O. V., Audu, C.T. & Ajayi, E. E. (2017). Influence of class size on students’ classroom discipline, engagement and communication: a study of senior secondary schools in Ekiti State Nigeria. *Sky Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 034 – 041.
- Ajayi, T. (2013). Revamping Public Secondary Education. Paper presented on the need for capacity building of school managers and teachers in Nigeria.
- Anakwue, A. L. (2021). Student-teacher relationship and academic achievement in Cross River state Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Current Research*. 8(9),374-386.

- Aoumeur, H. (2017). The Impact of Class Size on Teaching and Learning English as a Foreign Language: The Case of the Department of English at Abdelhamid Ibn Badis University . *Arab World English Journal*, 8(2), 123-135.
- Bagu, H. (2023). Effect of class size in effective teaching and learning of computer studies in junior secondary schools in Ushongo local government area of Benue state. *Journal of Open Science preprints*, 2(3) 123-334.
- Barde L.Y. Abubakar, A. A., Mohammed,S. Bizi, M. G., Ibrahim, N. and Uzoma,G.U. (2021).Analysis of large class-size and its effects on teaching and learning process among students’ secondary schools in Potiskum local government area. *Advanced Research and Reviews*, 8(01), 0.45–052
- Blatchford, P., Bassett, P., & Brown, P. (2021). Examining the Effect of Class Size on Classroom Engagement and Teacher-Pupil Interaction: Differences in Relation to Pupil Prior Attainment and Primary vs. Secondary Schools. *Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 21(2)715-730.
- Ehrenberg, R.G.; Brewer. D.J.; Gamorran A. & Williams ,D.J (2015). Class Size and student Achievement. *Psycgological science in the Public interest*, 2 (1), 1-30
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, (FRN 2014.) *National Policy on Education*, NERDC. P32.
- Garba, H.S., Shika, M.I. & Tukur, A.A. (2023) Impact of class size on students’ academic performance in chemistry among selected public senior secondary schools in Sabon Gari local government area of Kaduna state. *Rima International Journal of Education (RIJE)*, 2(1) 36 – 44.
- Igbinoba, E. E (2016). Effect of conflict management strategies on academic staff productivity in selected public and private universities in south- west Nigeria.
- Ihekoronye, E. O. (2020) Conducive school environment: A necessary factor for effective teaching and learning in public. *BSUJEM*, 2 (1) 202- 213.
- Ishii, S. (2021). The effect of class size on teacher-student interaction Hiroshima University, Japan Faculty of School Education, Professor
- Kolesnikova, I. V. (2016). Model of teaching to select the methods of education during general didactical training process for future primary school teachers. [In Ukrainian.] *Science and Education a New Dimension. Pedagogy and Psychology*, 38(77), 33-37.
- Kusi, H., & Manful, H. O. (2019). Class Size and Academic Performance of Students in Selected Nursing and Midwifery Training Colleges in the Central Region, Ghana. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 6(9) 224-246.
- Kweku, E. & Antwi, T. (2015). Instructional, psychological and social effects of large classes on Students of the Department of Basic Education, University of Education, Winneba, Ghana. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 3(3) 1-20.
- Lin, C. H., Zheng, B., and Zhang, Y. (2017). Interactions and learning outcomes in online language courses. *British Journal Educational Technology*, 48, 730–748. doi: 10.1111/bjet.12457
- O’banon (2016). Planning for instructional method. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), 2016. <http://www.feuked/rbanon/in/strategies/htm>.
- Swift, C. (2015). Class size and students’ performance in Mathematics, New Evidence from population variation. *Quarterly Journey of Mathematics* ,115(2), 1239-1268
- Taofeek, A. Yusuf, C A. Onifade, and Bello, O S. (2016). Impact of Class Size on Learning, Behavioral and General Attitudes of Students in Secondary Schools in Abeokuta, Ogun State Nigeria. *Journal of Research Initiatives*, 2(1),124-136.
- Wangui, M. F, Ombui, K., & Iravo, M. (2016). Effects of Work-Related Stress on Teachers Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kikuyu Sub County, Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 1(6)1645-1652.